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Safeguarding the Past: Monitoring Climate Change at Kalapodi Sanctuary through the TRIQUETRA Project

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Kalapodi archaeological site is located in central Greece, in the region of present-day Fthiotis consisting of a complex of temples and surrounding remains. It comprises a very important sanctuary, being among the most significant of ancient Phokis, providing crucial insights into Greek religious practices and architectural forms from the Mycenaean to the Classical periods. The archaeological site in Kalapodi has been the focus of extensive cultural heritage management efforts by the German Archaeological Institute (DAI) since 2017.

As a case study in the TRIQUETRA program, funded by the EU Horizon Europe research and innovation program (GA No. 101094818), this site exemplifies the challenges posed by climate change on cultural heritage. TRIQUETRA project aims to develop an integrated methodological model to safeguard archaeological remains, such as those at Kalapodi, from environmental risks and mainly frost. Central to the project is the creation of an evidence-based assessment platform for precise risk stratification, coupled with a comprehensive database of mitigation measures.

In this paper we would like to leverage environmental data and materials analysis from Kalapodi, so as to quantify the impacts of climate change and propose tailored preservation strategies. These include assessing the effects of frost on ancient structures and implementing preventative measures to ensure their long-term stability. To achieve this a pilot site has been designed and constructed on which several monitoring equipment has been attached to understand the influence of environmental conditions on the pilot and hence the ancient monument. The acquired knowledge and the methodology followed highlights the importance of combining scientific research and heritage management to address climate-related challenges and protect cultural heritage for future generations.